

Frequency and Distribution of ABO and Rh Blood Groups Among the in-Patients at a Tertiary Hospital in Northern Telangana

Swathi Samala¹, M. Lavanya², Farida Begum³, Smitha Vadana⁴, R. Nagarjuna Chary⁵

¹Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College, Nizamabad, Telangana, India.

²Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Nizamabad, Telangana, India.

³Associate professor, Department of Pathology, Nizamabad, Telangana, India.

⁴Assistant professor Department of Pathology, Nizamabad, Telangana, India.

⁵Professor and HOD, Department of Pathology, Nizamabad, Telangana, India.

Received: 15-04-2022 / Revised: 20-05-2022 / Accepted: 05-06-2022

Corresponding author: Dr. Smitha Vadana

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: International Society of Blood Transfusion has recently recognized 33 blood group system however the ABO system and rhesus (Rh) blood group remain clinically most important. After ABO blood group and Rh blood grouping discovered by Landsteiner and Weiner in 1901 and 1941 respectively, these two systems have proved to be the most important systems. Based on presence of the antigens and agglutinins human blood is divided into four major blood groups A, B, AB and O, based on which transfusions are made. The present study aims to investigate the ABO and rhesus (Rh) blood group frequency in the in-patients of Government general hospital, Nizamabad, Telangana state, over a period of 3 years from 2019 January to 2021 December.

Method: The retrospective study was conducted on more than thirty thousand in-patients including both male and female patients admitted to the government general Hospital, Nizamabad. Blood samples were taken from each subject and subsequently ABO and Rh blood groups were evaluated separately by using commercially available standard poly clonal antisera applying on the slide by using Tile Agglutination techniques. And all relevant data of patients were collected from blood bank department of the hospital.

Results: Out of 45352 individuals, 29932 (66%) were males and 15420(34%) were female individuals. The most common blood group found was O positive (33%) and least common being AB negative (1%). The prevalence of Rhesus positive and negative distribution in the present studied population was found as 93.9% and 6.1%, respectively.

Conclusion: The present study is useful in providing information on the status of ABO and Rh-D blood group distribution in the district of the Nizamabad and knowledge of it will help in effective management of regional blood transfusion services of the area.

Keywords: ABO and Rh blood group, frequency and distribution of blood groups.

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Background

Karl Landsteiner discovered ABO and Rh blood grouping systems in homosapiens and suggested the letters O, A, B and AB to express blood groups which were universally followed by the early 1950s[1,2] In 1907, Reuben Ottenberg started the first practical use of blood typing and it applied on a large scale during the First World War (1914–1915) [3]. Multiple alleles of ABO blood groups are located on a single locus of long arm of ninth chromosome (9q34) that exhibit Mendelian inheritance pattern [4]

ABO gene has mainly three types of alleles: i expresses no antigen hence type O, I A expresses type A antigen, and I B expresses type B antigen where I is a designation for iso-agglutinogen[5] Both I A and I B are dominant over i, and only ii people have type O blood group. I AI B individual has both phenotypes due to co dominance and is typed as AB blood group. Rh is the second major blood group system which comprises of more than 50 blood group antigens. Out of them, RHD and RHCE are the most clinically important Rh antigens. RHD and RHCE are closely linked genes on chromosome 1 that controls expression of Rh proteins [6]

Blood group distribution of any region can be influenced by race, ethnicity, geographical conditions, genetic drift and migration frequency of population. Environment factors and natural selection for survival of population in that region also affect the blood group distribution. The study of distribution of blood groups is of great importance for inventory management, safe blood transfusion, disease association with blood group in specific area and preparation of donor data for organ transplantation [7,8]

Methods

The present study is a retrospective observational study conducted at Government general hospital, Nizamabad over a period of 3 years from January 2019

to December 2021. We analysed the data of the in patients admitted in Government general hospital, Nizamabad. A total of 45352 in-patients were admitted during this period. The patient records were retrieved from the medical records department and were analysed, the records of all individuals between the age groups of 10 years to 70 years were included. Data of patients were collected like personal details, demographic details, occupational and medical history. The blood grouping of these patients was done by using the commercially available standard poly clonal antisera (arkray) applying on the tile by using slide agglutination techniques. In this method tile is divided into three parts as for each part, a drop of patient blood is mixed with anti A, anti B, anti D separately. The agglutination or blood clumping pattern can be visually observed from which the ABO and rhesus D (Rh D) type of blood can be determined. Although many other methods like test tube method, microplate method, column agglutination technique are available, we use the classical tile method and when in doubt the test tube method is employed. The patient data is analysed using the MS- excel sheet and appropriate statistical analysis was done. The incidence of various blood groups was analysed. The most common blood and least common among the different genders and age groups was studied.

Results

Blood groups of 45352 patients were analysed. The test was done by using of tile agglutination method. The patient load over a period of 3 years from 2019 January to 2021 December was included in the study. From our study, it is observed that majority of the patients belonged to blood group O positive 14931(33%) least common being AB negative 429 (1%). And other groups include A positive belongs to 12273 (27%) and this is the second most common group, followed by

B positive 12073 (26.6%), AB positive 3356 (7.3%), A negative 745 (1.6%), B negative (1.7%), O negative (1.8%)

Out of 45352 individuals, 29932 (66%) were males and 15420 (34%) were female

individuals. The prevalence of Rhesus positive and negative distribution in the present studied population was found as 93.9% and 6.1%, respectively.

Figure 1: Gender Distribution

Figure 2: Rh frequency

Table 1: Frequency distribution of blood groups in 2019,2020,2022

Blood groups	2019	2020	2021	Total
A+ve	4120(25%)	3503 (26%)	4650(29.2%)	12273(27%)
B+ ve	4719(30%)	3811(29%)	3548(22.5%)	12073(26.6%)
AB+ve	1243(7.7%)	847(6%)	1266(8%)	3356(7.3%)
O+ve	5006(31.5%)	4430(33% %)	5489(34.5%)	14931(33%)
A-ve	266(1.6%)	233(1.7%)	246(1.5%)	745(1.6%)
B-ve	255(1.5%)	225(1.6%)	278(1.6%)	758(1.7%)
AB-ve	157(1%)	129(1%)	143(1%)	429(1%)
O-ve	271(1.7%)	231(1.7%)	286(1.7%)	788(1.8%)
Total	16037	13409	15906	45352

Figure 3: Frequency distribution of blood groups in 2019,2020 & 2021

Table 2: Gender wise frequency distribution of blood groups in 2019,2020,2022(%)

	2019		2020		2021		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
A+ve	2472 (25%)	1648 (26%)	2137 (26%)	1366 (26%)	2790 (28%)	1860 (30%)	12273
B+ve	2925 (29%)	1794 (18%)	2286 (28%)	1525 (29%)	2199 (22%)	1349 (22%)	12073
AB+ve	758 (7.7%)	485 (7.8%)	508 (6.2%)	339 (6.4%)	772 (7.8%)	494 (8.1%)	3356
O+ve	3103 (31%)	1903 (30%)	2746 (33%)	1684 (32%)	3514 (35%)	1997 (32%)	14931
A-ve	159(1.6%)	107(1.7%)	138(1.6%)	93(1.%)	147(1.4%)	99(1.6%)	745
B-ve	153(1.5%)	102(1.6%)	130(1.5%)	95(1.8%)	172(1.7%)	106(1.7%)	758
AB-ve	91(0.9%)	66(1.0%)	77(0.9%)	52(0.9%)	84(0.8%)	59(0.9%)	429
O-ve	163(1.6%)	108(1.7%)	140(1.7%)	91(1.7%)	185(1.8%)	101(1.6%)	788
Total	9824	6213	8162	5225	9863	6065	45352

Discussion

The term “blood group” refers to the entire blood group system comprising red blood cell (RBC) antigens whose specificity is controlled by a series of genes which can be allelic or linked very closely on the same chromosome. “Blood type” refers to a specific pattern of reaction to testing antisera within a given system. Over a period of time, our understanding on blood groups has evolved to encompass not only transfusion-related problems but also specific disease association with RBC surface antigens. Karl Landsteiner has been credited for the discovery of ABO

blood group system in 1909. His extensive research on serology based on simple but strong scientific reasoning led to identification of major blood groups such as O, A, and B types, compatibility testing, and subsequent transfusion practices. He was awarded Noble Prize in 1930 for this discovery. His obituary lists an immense contribution of more than 346 publications. Later, Jan Jansky described classification of human blood groups of four types. Among the 33 systems, ABO remains the most important in transfusion and transplantation since any person above

the age of 6 months possess clinically significant anti-A and/or anti-B antibodies in their serum. Blood group A contains antibody against blood group B in serum

and vice-versa, while blood group O contains no A/B antigen but both their antibodies in serum [10].

Table 3: Distribution of blood groups in India

Population	A	B	AB	O	Rh positive	Rh negative
Northern India						
1. Lucknow [11]	21.73	39.84	9.33	29.10	95.71	4.29
2. Punjab [12]	21.91	37.56	9.3	31.21	97.3	2.7
3. Jodhpur [13]	22.2	36.4	9.4	31.7	91.75	8.25
Western India						
4. Western Ahmedabad [14]	21.94	34.90	7.86	30.79	95.0	4.95
5. Eastern Ahmedabad [15]	23.30	35.50	8.80	32.50	94.20	5.80
6. Surat [16]	24.10	34.89	8.69	32.32	94.18	5.82
7. Maharashtra [17]	23.38	31.89	8.72	30.99	95.36	4.64
Eastern India						
8. Durgapur [18]	23.90	33.60	7.70	34.80	94.70	5.30
Southern India						
9. Bangalore [19]	23.85	29.95	6.37	39.82	94.2	5.8
10. Vellore [20]	21.86	32.69	6.70	38.75	94.5	5.5
11. Devangere [21]	26.15	29.85	7.24	31.76	94.8	5.2
12. Shimoga- Malnad [22]	24.27	29.43	7.13	39.17	94.93	5.07
Present study	27	26.6	7.3	33	93.1	6.9

We compared our results with other studies carried out in different regions of India and worldwide. Our study O positive is more common followed by A group, B group, AB group, followed by O negative, B negative, A negative and AB negative. The study done in Eastern India by Durgapur *et al* [18], in Southern India by Bangalore *et al*, vellore *et al*, Devenagere *et al*, shimoga malnad *et al* showed blood group O [19-22] was the commonest and

these results are correlated with our study.

The study done in Northern India by Chandra *et al* Lucknow, Sindhu *et al* Punjab and Behra *et al* Jodhpur showed blood group B was the commonest, followed by O, A and AB. Our study does not correlate with these studies [11-13].

In above all study groups and present study group Rh positive group was most common that is accounts for all most 96%.

Table 4: Frequency of blood groups in different countries

Britain [22]	42.0	8.0	3.0	47.0	83	17
USA [23]	41.0	9.0	4.0	46.0	85	15
Nigeria [24]	21.60	21.40	2.80	54.20	95.20	4.80
N. Guinea [25]	22.50	23.70	4.70	48.90	95.90	4.10
Saudi Arabia [26]	24.0	17.0	4.0	52.0	93.0	7.0
Pakistan [27]	22.40	32.40	8.40	30.50	93.0	7.0
Nepal [28]	34.0	29.0	4.0	32.50	96.70	3.30

Outside India, studies were carried out in different countries of the world like Britain, USA, Nigeria, New Guinea, Saudi Arabia, Pakistan and Nepal. All countries,

except Pakistan and Nepal22-28, showed O blood group to be most common in their respective studies, which is similar from our observations, as O blood group was

commonest in our study followed by A, B, AB groups.

Conclusion

From our study, we established that among the various ABO and Rh-D blood groups, group O (33%) is the commonest, followed next in frequency by blood group A (27%) and then blood group B (26.6%).

The present study is therefore useful in providing information on the status of ABO and Rh-D blood group distribution in Government General Hospital, Nizamabad and knowledge of it will help us in effective management of regional blood transfusion services of the area. The study helps to prepare a database for the hospital and blood banks and creates awareness as to which blood groups should be stored and given importance. So, it is advisable to do blood grouping studies in each region for drafting proper national transfusion policies and for supplying blood to the needy patients during emergency

Reference

- Garratty G, Dzik W, Issitt PD, *et al.*: Terminology for blood group antigens and genes-historical origins and guidelines in the new millennium. *Transfusion* 2000; 40:477-89
- Deepthi S, Singh SB, Maruthy KN, *et al.*: Distribution frequency of ABO and rhesus blood groups among medical students-A study from Narayana Medical College and Hospital in South India. *Int J Health Sci Res* 2015; 5(9):5
- Durand JK, Wills MS, Karl Landsteiner MD: *Laboratory Medicine*. 2010; 41:3
- Crow JF: Felix Bernstein and the first human marker locus. *Genetics* 1993; 133:4-7
- Klug SW, Cummings RM: *Concepts of Genetics*, 5th edn. vol.1. Upper saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 1997:1.
- Johnson TS, Marilyn W: *The Rh Blood Group System. Modern Blood Banking & Transfusion Practices*. 6th ed. 4838/24, Ansari Road, Daryaganj, New Delhi 110002, India: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers(P) Ltd; 2012: 22.
- Suresh B, Babu Sreedhar KV, Mouli PC, *et al.*: Distribution of ABO and rhesus (D) blood group antigens among blood donors at a tertiary care teaching hospital blood bank in south India. *J Clin Sci Res* 2015; 4:129-35
- Vandana R, Kumar VA, Pradeep K: A Study of ABO and Rh (D) Blood Groups among Kurmi (Backward Caste) of Jaunpur District. *Anthropologist* 2009; 11:305-6
- Owen R. Karl Landsteiner and the first human marker locus. *Genetics* 2000; 155:995-8.
- Blood groups systems Ranadhir Mitra, Nitasha Mishra, Girija Prasad Rath. Department of Neuroanaesthesiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi, India *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia* | Vol. 58 | Issue 5 | Sep-Oct 2014
- Sidhu S, Sidhu LS. ABO blood group frequencies among the Sansis of Punjab. *Coll Anthropol*. 1980; 4:55.
- Behra R, Joshi YR. Distribution of ABO blood group and RH (D) factor in western Rajasthan. *National J Medical Res* 2013; 3:73-5.
- Wadhwa MK, Patel SM, Kothari DC, Pandey M, Patel DD. Distribution of ABO and Rhesus-D groups in Gujarat, India: a hospital-based study. *Indian J Ped Oncol*. 1998;19(4):137-41.
- Patel PA, Patel SP, Shah JV, OzaHaren V. Frequency and distribution of blood groups in blood donors in western Ahmedabad – a hospital-based study. *National J Med Res*. 2012;2(2):207-10.
- Mehta N, Swadas B. Prevalence of ABO blood
- Giri PA, Yadav S, Parhar GS, Phalke DB. Frequency of ABO and Rhesus blood groups: A study from a rural tertiary care teaching hospital in India. *Int J Biol Med Res*. 2011; 2:988-90.

17. Nag I, Das SS. ABO and Rhesus blood groups in potential blood donors at Durgapur steel city of the district of Burdwan West Bengal. *Asian J Transfus Sci.* 2012; 6:54-5.
18. Periyavan A, Sangeetha SK, Marimuthu P, Manjunath BK, Seema. Distribution of ABO and Rh-D groups in and around Bangalore. *Asian J Transfus Sci.* 2010; 4:41.
19. Das PK, Nair SC, Harris VK, Rose D, Mammen JJ, Bose YN, Sudarsanam A. Distribution of ABO and Rh-D blood groups among blood donors in a tertiary care centre in South India. *Trop Doct.* 2001; 31:47-8.
20. Mallikarjuna S. Prevalence of ABO and Rhesus blood group among blood donors. *Ind J Pub Health Res Develop.* 2012; 3:106-9.
21. Girish CJ, Chandrashekhar TN, Ramesh Babu K, Kantikar SM. ABO and Rhesus blood group distribution among Malnad region blood donors. *Res Rev Biomed Biotech.* 2011;2(3):25-30.
22. Frances TF. In: *Common Laboratory and Diagnostic Tests.* 3rd Edition. Philadelphia: Lippincott. Blood groups (ABO groups); 2002: 15-19
23. Mollison PL, Engelfriet CP, Conteras M. In *Blood Transfusion in Clinical Medicine.* 9th Edition. Oxford: Blackwell Scientific Publication. The Rh blood Group system; 1993: 2008-9.
24. Mwangni J. Blood group distribution in an urban population of patient targeted blood donors. *East Afr Med J.* 1999;76(11):615-8.
25. Loua A, Lamah MR, Haba NY, Camara M. Frequency of blood groups ABO and Rhesus D in the Guinea population. *Tranfus Clin Biol.* 2007; 14:435-9.
26. Bashwari LA, Al Mulhim AA, Ahmad MS, Ahmed MA. Frequency of ABO blood groups in Eastern region of Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Med J.* 2001; 22:1008-12.
27. Khan MI, Micheal S, Akhtar F, Naveed A, Ahmed A, Qamar R. Association of ABO blood groups with glaucoma in the Pakistani population. *Canadian J Ophthalmol.* 2009;44(5):582-6.
28. Pramanik T, Pramanik S. Distribution of ABO and Rh blood groups in Nepalese medical students: a report. *East Mediterr Health J.* 2000;6(1):156-8.